

small (1,000 ha) area; 2) destruction of natural enemies *Cyrtorhinus* sp., spiders, and egg parasites of BPH because of heavy insecticide use to control BPH, leafroller, and armyworm; and 3) failure to control BPH or BPH resurgence because of in-

effective coverage of aerial insecticide sprays, especially at late crop stages.

To combat these problems, increasing emphasis is placed on pest control through integrated pest management and a substantial reduction in the use of highly

toxic, broad-spectrum insecticides. We also are changing from continuous cropping to planting two crops per year with a fallow period. New resistant varieties are being introduced. □

Chemical control of rice gall midge (GM) and leafhopper (LF)

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We evaluated the effectiveness of chlorpyrifos seedling root dip and granular carbofuran application for controlling GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) and LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenee in 1981-83 kharif.

Ten days after sowing the nursery, carbofuran 3% granules were applied: 40 kg/ha in 1981 and 20 kg/ha in 1983. The nursery was unprotected in 1982.

At transplanting, we compared 12-h and 3-h seedling root dips in chlorpyrifos 0.02% in a 1% urea solution. In 1983, we also evaluated a root treatment with chlorpyrifos 0.02%-treated carbono phosphate slurry. The amount of carbono phosphate needed for P fertilizer for the main field area (at 300 kg/ha, equal to 60 kg P/ha) was mixed 3:1 with wet clay and water was added to make a thick slurry. Chlorpyrifos 20 EC was mixed in the slurry at 0.02% concentration. The roots of seedlings were uniformly coated with the slurry and planted after 5-10 min. At planting, the field was puddled and had little standing water.

Carbofuran 3% granules at 20 kg/ha were applied to all chlorpyrifos-treated plots 20 d after transplanting (DT). Water was impounded for 3 d after granular application. The trial was in a randomized block design in 4 replications with an untreated control. Jaya was planted in 10 × 5-m plots at 20 × 15-cm spacing. Soil was a sandy loam.

GM damage was recorded at 45 and 60 DT and LF damage at 75 DT. All treated plots were GM free in 1981 and 1983. In 1982, damage until 45 DT was low, but beyond 60 DT, there was no significant difference between treated and untreated plots (Table 1). This was

Table 1. Chemical control of GM and LF at Goa, India, 1981-83.^a

Treatments ^b	Silvershoot (%)		LF damage (%)	Productive tillers/hill (no.)
	45 DT	60 DT		
1981				
A	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.5 a	8.9 a
B	0.0 a	0.0 a	1.0 a	7.3 b
Control	16.0 b	35.7 b	7.7 b	4.7 c
1982				
A	6.0 a	34.7 b	3.6 a	7.1 a
B	4.7 a	21.7 a	3.9 a	6.5 a
Control	36.7 b	28.1 a	33.1 b	4.9 b
1983				
A	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	7.3 a
B	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	7.3 a
C	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	7.1 a
Control	10.8 b	18.0 b	15.9 b	6.7 a

^aIn a column in a particular year, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bA = NP + RD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 12 h fb 20 kg carbofuran 3% gr 20 DT. B = NP + RD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 3 h in 1% urea solution fb 20 kg carbofuran 3% 20 DT. C = NP + RT with chlorpyrifos 0.02% treated CP slurry for 5-10 min fb 20 kg carbofuran 3% gr on 20 DT. NP = nursery protection with carbofuran 3% gr @ 40 kg and 20 kg/ha, respectively during 1981 and 1983. RD = root dip, RT = root treatment, fb = followed by, CP = carbono phosphate, gr = granule, DT = days after transplanting.

Table 2. Yields and economics of insect control in chemical control trials at Goa, India, 1981-1983.^a

Treatment ^b	Yield ^c (t/ha)	Gross profit ^d (\$/ha)	Cost of insecticide application ^e (\$/ha)	Net gain ^f (\$/ha)	Gain from insecticides ^g (\$/ha)	Benefit:cost ^h
1981						
A	4.7 a	611	43	568	217	6.1
B	4.4 a	572	44	528	177	5.0
Control	2.7 b	351	0	351	—	—
1982						
A	3.4 a	442	37	405	249	7.7
B	3.3 a	429	38	391	235	7.2
Control	1.2 b	156	0	156	—	—
1983						
A	3.5 a	455	40	415	90	3.3
B	3.6 a	468	41	427	102	3.5
C	3.5 a	455	40	415	90	3.3
Control	2.5 b	325	0	325	—	—

^aAt conversion rate of US\$1 = Rs 13.02. ^bSee Table 1 for treatment details. ^cIn a column in a particular year, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^dGrain yield in kg/ha at 14% moisture × 0.13. ^e\$1.96 for labor + cost of insecticide including the cost of urea. ^fGross profit - cost of insecticide application. ^gNet gain of treatment - net gain of control. ^h(Gross profit of treatment - gross profit of control) + cost of insecticide application.

primarily because the unprotected seedlings from the nursery had 5.4% GM infestation.

LF was effectively controlled in all

treated plots (Table 1), which had more productive tillers and significantly higher yield than the untreated control (Table 2). □